

A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY OF AGNIKARMA WITH KAMSYA SHALAKA AND LOHA SHALAKA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF VATAKANTAKA W.S.R. TO PLANTAR FASCIITIS

Dr. Vanishri Umapati Hiremath^{1*}, Dr. Anumarlapudi Jayaram²

*¹PG Scholar, Department of *Shalya Tantra*, Ramakrishna Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Ramagondanahalli, Yelahanka, Bengaluru.

²Professor and H.O.D., Post Graduate Department of *Shalya Tantra*, Ramakrishna Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Ramagondanahalli, Yelahanka, Bengaluru.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Vanishri Umapati Hiremath

PG Scholar, Department of *Shalya Tantra*, Ramakrishna Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital & Research Centre, Ramagondanahalli, Yelahanka, Bengaluru.

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ABSTRACT

Background of the Study: Among all the *Vatavyadhi*, *Vatakantaka* is one of the important *Vyadhi*. *Acharya Sushruta* mentioned the concept of *Vatakantaka* as it occurs mainly due to walking on the uneven surface and due to *Shrama*. Due to which Vitiated *Vata Dosha* accumulates at the heel region and cause severe pain. The present study, *Agnikarma* with *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka* in two different groups were used to evaluate their efficacy in the management of *Vatakantaka*. **Objectives of the Study:** 1. To critically review classical and contemporary literature relating to *Agnikarma*, *Vatakantaka*, and Plantar Fasciitis. 2. To clinically assess the effectiveness of *Agnikarma* performed with *Kamsya Shalaka* in patients with *Vatakantaka*. 3. To clinically assess the effectiveness of *Agnikarma* performed with *Loha Shalaka* in patients with *Vatakantaka*. 4. To systematically compare the outcomes of *Agnikarma* administered with *Kamsya Shalaka* versus *Loha Shalaka* in the treatment of *Vatakantaka*. **Study Desing:** This study is a randomized

comparative clinical study in which 40 patients diagnosed with *Vatakantaka*, fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria, were selected and randomly allocated into two groups Group

A (Trial Group) and Group B Standard Group) – each consisting of 20 patients. Assessment was carried out before treatment and after treatment based on subjective and objective criteria. Group A (Trial Group) treated with *Agnikarma* using *Kamsya Shalaka* was administered once a week interval for a total of 4 sessions. Group B (Standard Group) treated with *Agnikarma* using *Loha Shalaka* was administered once a week interval for a total of 4 sessions. **Results and conclusion:** The effect of the treatment in both the groups was assessed by applying Statistical tests: Mann Whitney U test – Between the groups and Wilcoxon test – Within the groups respectively. Both Group Patients had better results from *Agnikarma* using both *Shalakas*. However, Group A (Trial Group) – *Kamsya Shalaka Agnikarma* demonstrated superior results in terms of symptomatic relief compared to Group B (Standard Group) – *Loha Shalaka Agnikarma*. It can be concluded from the study that in the management of *Vatakantaka*, *Agnikarma with Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka Chikitsa* plays an important role in cure.

KEYWORDS: *Vatakantaka; Agnikarma; Kamsya Shalaka; Loha Shalaka; Plantar Fasciitis.*

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the ancient science of life, is structured upon eight branches known as *Ashtanga Ayurveda*, among which *Shalya Tantra* deals with surgical and para surgical procedures for the management of various disorders. One such condition described in classical texts is *Vatakantaka*.^[1] caused due to the aggravation of *Vata Dosha* and affecting the *Khudaka Pradesh*, presenting chiefly as pricking heel pain. The clinical manifestation of *Vatakantaka*^[2] corresponds closely to Plantar Fasciitis in contemporary medicine, which is a commonly encountered cause of heel pain among middle-aged and elderly individuals. The increasing prevalence of musculoskeletal disorders, lifestyle-related strain and occupational stress highlights the necessity of effective, affordable and sustainable treatment modalities. Plantar Fasciitis^[3] is characterized by degenerative and inflammatory changes of the plantar fascia due to repetitive micro-trauma. It is commonly seen in persons with prolonged standing, running, improper footwear and abnormal foot mechanics. The condition significantly affects daily functioning.^[4] Contemporary management includes analgesics, physiotherapy, corticosteroid injections and surgical release. However, these offer limited sustained relief and recurrence is common.^[5]

Agnikarma is specially indicated for disorders involving *Twak, Mamsa, Sira, Snayu, Sandhi* and *Asthi* where *Vata Dosha* predominates. *Acharya Sushruta* states that *Agnikarma*^[6] is

superior to *Bhesaja*, *Kshara Karma* and *Shashtra Karma* due to its immediate and sustained pain-relieving effect and minimal recurrence. *Agnikarma*^[7,8] with *Shalakas* of different metals is described in the classics. *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka* are specifically advised when *Dosha-Dushya Samurchana* occurs in *Mamsa Dhatu*. The controlled heat application relieves *Srotorodha*, *pacifies Vata* and *Kapha*, improves circulation and restores functional mobility.^[9]

Although *Agnikarma* is widely practiced for *Vatakantaka*, comparative clinical evaluation of different *Shalakas*, especially *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka*, is limited. Both differ in heat retention, tissue penetration, and local therapeutic response. Therefore, a systematic comparative evaluation is necessary to establish which *Shalaka* provides better clinical outcomes.

The present study aims to bridge this gap and contribute to evidence-based clinical practice in *Ayurveda* and *Shalya Tantra*. In both groups, the procedure of *Agnikarma* was carried out in a uniform manner. In Group A, *Agnikarma* was performed with *Kamsya Shalaka*^[10] (trial group) and in Group B, *Agnikarma* was performed with *Loha Shalaka*^[11] (standard group). The heat application in both groups was continued until *Samyak Dagdha Lakshana* was observed. After the procedure, *Ghrita Kumari* was applied to soothe the affected area and to reduce the burning sensation. *Triphala Guggulu* was administered orally for both groups. Follow-up examinations were conducted during and after the completion of therapy to evaluate improvement and any recurrence. Hence, the present study is undertaken with the Title: A comparative clinical study of *Agnikarma* with *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka* in the management of *Vatakantaka* W.S.R to Plantar Fasciitis.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To critically review classical and contemporary literature relating to *Agnikarma*, *Vatakantaka*, and Plantar Fasciitis.
2. To clinically assess the effectiveness of *Agnikarma* performed with *Kamsya Shalaka* in patients with *Vatakantaka*.
3. To clinically assess the effectiveness of *Agnikarma* performed with *Loha Shalaka* in patients with *Vatakantaka*.
4. To systematically compare the outcomes of *Agnikarma* administered with *Kamsya Shalaka* versus *Loha Shalaka* in the treatment of *Vatakantaka*.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study is a randomized comparative clinical study in which 40 patients diagnosed with *Vatakantaka*, fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria, were selected and randomly allocated into two groups – Group A (Trial Group) and Group B (Standard Group) – each consisting of 20 patients. Assessment was carried out before treatment and after treatment based on subjective and objective criteria.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients presenting with heel pain characterized by first-step pain, worsening after periods of rest and physical activity.
2. Age between 20 and 60 years, regardless of sex.
3. Patients who have not experienced adequate relief from prior conventional treatments for the same condition.
4. Patients deemed medically fit to undergo *Agnikarma* therapy.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Patients testing positive for HIV, HBsAg, rheumatoid factor, or diagnosed with malignancies.
2. Individuals with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus, uncontrolled hypertension, or deformities / dislocation of the ankle joint.
3. Pregnant women.
4. Lactating women.
5. Elderly patients beyond the specified age criteria.
6. Patients below 20 years of age

WITHDRAWAL CRITERIA

- Participants who develop any serious medical condition, severe complications, or significant worsening of disease symptoms requiring urgent medical intervention will be withdrawn from the study and managed appropriately.
- Participants who choose to voluntarily withdraw or discontinue their participation in the study at any point will be allowed to do so without any penalty or loss of benefits.

DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA

The diagnosis of *Vatakantaka* (corresponding to Plantar Fasciitis) is established based on the following clinical features described in classical *Ayurvedic* literature, supplemented by modern clinical observations:

- *Khudaka Pradesha Shoola* - Pain localized to the region of the heel.
- *Stambha* - Stiffness or rigidity in the affected foot.
- *Daha* - Sensation of burning or warmth in the area.
- *Sotha* - Swelling around the heel or plantar surface.
- Marked discomfort or pain at the heel, especially upon standing or walking.
- First-step pain - Sharp pain experienced during the initial steps after a period of rest.
- Presence of tenderness upon examination of the heel region.

INVESTIGATIONS

The following investigations were performed to support diagnosis, assess eligibility, and ensure patient safety prior to and during the study.

1. X-ray: Conducted if clinically indicated, to evaluate structural abnormalities of the heel and rule out other pathologies.
2. Complete Blood Count (CBC): To assess general health status and exclude underlying infections or significant haematological abnormalities.
3. Random Blood Sugar (RBS): To screen for diabetes mellitus.
4. HIV Test: To exclude participants with HIV infection.
5. Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAG): To rule out hepatitis B infection.
6. Glycated Hemoglobin (HbA1C): To evaluate glycemic control in suspected diabetic patients.
7. Rheumatoid Factor (RA factor): To screen for rheumatoid arthritis and related autoimmune conditions.
8. Uric Acid: To rule out Gout Arthritis.

PLAN OF INTERVENTIONS

Sample and grouping: A total of 40 patients who met the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Participants were randomly assigned to two groups—Group A and Group B—each consisting of 20 patients. Allocation was done irrespective of sex, age, or severity of condition.

GROUP-A (Trail Group): The patients of Group A were subjected to *Agnikarma* performed with *Kamsya Shalaka* for once a week – 1st day, 7th Day, 14th Day and 21st days interval.

GROUP-B (Standard Group): The patients of Group B were subjected to and *Agnikarma* performed with *Loha Shalaka* for once a week – 1st day, 7th Day, 14th Day and 21st days interval.

PROCEDURE: FOR BOTH GROUP A AND GROUP B

1. POORVA KARMA

A. Preparation of Tools and Equipment

- Collection of all necessary equipment needed for the *Agnikarma* procedure – sterile gloves, gauze pieces and pads, sponge-holding forceps, betadine solution, surgical spirit, sterile drapes, lighter, marker, needles, *Ghrita Kumari*, *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka*– were collected and made ready.
- Collection of all drugs required for treating the complications of *Atiyoga* and *Ayoga* of *Agnikarma*. The *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka* were procured from certified jewellery shops, ensuring the authenticity and quality of the metals used.

The *Kamsya Shalaka* and *Loha Shalaka* were procured from certified jewellery shops, ensuring the authenticity and quality of the metals used.

Table No. 1: Name and Parts used of Ingredients in *Kamsya Shalaka*.

Sl. No	Name	Sanskrit Name:	Used:
1.	Copper	Tamra	88%
2.	Tin	Vanga	12%

Table No 2: Name and Parts used of Ingredients in *Loha Shalaka*.

Sl. No:	Name:	Sanskrit Name:	Used:
1	Iron	<i>Loha</i>	100%

B. Preparation of the Medicine

- *Triphala Guggulu* was obtained from the GMP-certified our college Ramakrishna Ayurveda College Pharmacy.

C. Preparation of the Patient

- Patients were selected after meeting the inclusion criteria and written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to the intervention.

- A dedicated room for conducting *Agnikarma* was arranged, ensuring it was well-lit and protected from environmental factors such as direct airflow or dust.
- Patients were instructed to consume a meal of *Picchila Anna* (unctuous/soft rice preparation) before the procedure.
- Vital signs—including blood pressure, pulse rate, and temperature—were monitored and recorded.

2. PRADANA KARMA

GROUP A (Trail Group): *Agnikarma* performed with *Kamsya Shalaka* for once a week – 1st day, 7th Day, 14th Day and 21st days interval.

- 1) The participant was positioned comfortably.
- 2) Tender points over the heel were identified and marked with a marker.
- 3) The procedure site was disinfected using betadine solution.
- 4) Sterile drapes were used to maintain an aseptic field.
- 5) The *Kamsya Shalaka* was heated on a blue flame until red hot and applied to the marked points in a Bindu shape, carefully avoiding *Marma*, *Sira*, *Snayu*, and *Sandhi*.
- 6) *Agnikarma* was performed until “*Samyak Dagdha Lakshanas*” were observed— that is, the burn was neither too deep nor too superficial, the colour resembled a ripened palm fruit, and the wound appeared well-demarcated.
- 7) *Ghrita* and *Kumari* were applied topically on the treated site to alleviate any burning sensation.

❖ **GROUP B (Standard Group):** *Agnikarma* performed with *Loha Shalaka* for once a week – 1st day, 7th Day, 14th Day and 21st days interval.

- 1) The participant was similarly positioned for comfort.
- 2) Tender areas identified and marked.
- 3) Skin disinfected with betadine solution.
- 4) Sterile draping completed as above.
- 5) The *Loha Shalaka* was heated until red hot and applied to the marked points in *Bindu* shape, avoiding *Marma*, *Sira*, *Snayu*, and *Sandhi* regions.
- 6) *Agnikarma* was continued until *Samyak Dagdha Lakshanas* were achieved, using the same criteria as Group A.
- 7) *Ghrita* and *Kumari* were applied to reduce any immediate burning sensation post-procedure.

3. PASCHAT KARMA

- Vital signs were reassessed, and the patient's pain level was recorded using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS).
- Patients were instructed to avoid contact with water on the treated area for 24 hours following the procedure.
- Patients were scheduled for follow-up assessments of seven days to monitor healing and outcomes.

DURATION OF THE STUDY

Table No. 2: Duration of the study for both Group A and Group B.

Group	No. of Pt.	Procedure	Trial Duration	Follow up	Study Duration
Group A	20	<i>Agnikarma with Kamsya Shalaka</i>	21 Days	After 7 Days- on 28th Day	28 Days.
Group B	20	<i>Agnikarma with Loha Shalaka</i>	21 Days	After 7 Days- on 28th Day	28 Days.

ASSESSMENT DONE ON

Table No. 3: Assessment days for both Group A and Group B.

Sl. No.	In Group A – (Trail Group) <i>Agnikarma with Kamsya Shalaka</i>		In Group B – (Standard Group) <i>Agnikarma with Loha Shalaka</i>	
1.	B.T.– Before Treatment	On 0 th day	B.T.–Before Treatment	On 0 th day
2.	D.T.1 – During Treatment 1	On 7 th	D.T.1 – During Treatment 1	On 7 th
3.	D.T.2 – During Treatment 2	On 14 th day	D.T.2 – During Treatment 2	On 14 th day
4.	A.T. – After Treatment	On 21 th day	A.T. – After Treatment	On 21 th day
5.	A.F.–After Follow Up	On 28 th day	A.F.–After Follow Up	On 28 th day

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Day Assessment of the clinical study was done on the Subjective and Objective parameters based on the Case Proforma.

1. Subjective Criteria: 2 Parameters.
2. Objective Criteria: 1 Parameter.

CHART FOR GRADING OF SUBJECTIVE CRITERIA

Table No. 4: Gradings of Subjective Criteria for Group A and Group B.

Sl. No.	CRITERIA	GRADE	ASSESSMENT GRADING	VAS SCALE
1.	Shoola Pain (VAS - Visual Analogue Scale)	0	No Pain.	0 = No Pain
		1	Pain tolerable without any discomfort.	1 – 3 = Mild pain
		2	Pain that is distressing but	4 – 6 =

			manageable.	Moderate pain
		3	Pain described as excruciating and debilitating.	7 – 10 = Severe pain
2.	First Step Pain	0	No pain during the first step.	
		1	Pain lasts less than 10 minutes after the first step.	
		2	Pain persists between 11 to 30 minutes after the first step	
		3	Pain continues for more than 30 minutes before walking comfortably.	

OVER ALL ASSESSMENT OF PARAMETERS

Table No. 5: Gradings of Overall assessment for Group A and Group B.

SL. NO.	GRADE	CONDITION OF TREATMENT:	PERCENTAGE OF CURE:
1.	0	Cured	91% - 100% Improvement
2.	1	Marked Improvement	46% - 90% Improvement
3.	2	Moderate Improvement	0% - 45% Improvement

RESULTS

TOTAL MEAN OF ALL 3 PARAMETERS

❖ Overall Treatment Assessment After Treatment (BT-AT)

- Overall improvement Assessment **within Group A: 35.47%**
- Overall improvement Assessment within Group B: 16.73%
- On Comparing total Improvement **in between Group-A and Group-B** in Percentage after treatment- **68%: 32%**

❖ Overall Treatment Assessment After Follow up (BT-AF)

- Overall improvement Assessment **within Group A: 81.23%**
- Overall improvement Assessment within Group B: 61.63%
- On Comparing total Improvement **in between Group-A and Group-B** in Percentage after follow up - **57%: 43%**

Interpretation: On Analyzing above statistical test and results of Treatment in Group A & B – Both the Groups has equally good result in treating *Vata Kantaka* Patients, **Statistically**, Group-A Had overwhelming better response then group B

Clinically, Group-B shows also good results in patients.

- ❖ However, statistically when mean rank and mean were compared between groups.
- ❖ **Statistically:** Group A was comparatively better than Group B in **3 parameters** like Pain, First Step Pain and Local Tenderness.

Individually statistical parameters show as

1. In **Group-A** Pain has 84.21% relief and Group B has 58.13% relief.
2. In **Group-A** First Step Pain has 78.94% relief and Group B has 64.28% relief.
3. In **Group-A** Local Tenderness has 80.55% relief and Group B has 62.50% relief.

DISCUSSION

Vatakantaka, characterized by stiffness, pain, and restricted mobility in the affected region, and Plantar Fasciitis, manifesting as heel pain, tenderness, and difficulty during the first steps, are primarily due to *Vata* aggravation, leading to degeneration and rigidity of *Mamsa*, *Snayu* and other connective tissues. Modern treatments often provide only symptomatic relief, while Ayurvedic therapies like *Agnikarma* with *Kamsya Shalaka* or *Loha Shalaka* aim to correct the underlying *Vata* imbalance and restore normal function.

Plantar Fasciitis is a degenerative disorder of the plantar fascia, primarily affecting its origin at the medial calcaneal tuberosity. The pathology involves micro tears and inflammatory changes resulting from repetitive mechanical stress due to running, prolonged standing, walking or jumping. Predisposing factors include high arched feet, flat feet, obesity, pregnancy and improper footwear. Clinically, Plantar Fasciitis presents with heel pain, characteristically worse during the first steps in the morning, along with localized tenderness at the calcaneal insertion and pain aggravated by barefoot walking or climbing stairs.

Probable Mode of Action of *Kamsya Shalaka*

Kamsya Shalaka, composed predominantly of copper with tin as a secondary component, plays a significant role in *Agnikarma* due to its superior heat-retention and controlled heat-release characteristics. Copper, being the major constituent, possesses *Ushna* and *Tikshna* qualities and is known to pacify *Vata*. Its inherent properties facilitate deep penetration of

heat into the affected *Mamsa*, *Snayu* and *Sandhi*, thereby enhancing local microcirculation, reducing stagnation, improving tissue oxygenation and relieving stiffness. Continuous, stable conduction of heat promotes *Srotoshodhana*, helping in clearing subtle obstructions and supporting nourishment of local *Dhatu*s. Tin, though present in smaller percentage, provides stabilizing support and ensures uniform heat diffusion, thereby preventing excessive burning or uneven cauterization.

Kamsya Shalaka appears to offer superior analgesic, anti-inflammatory and *Vata*-pacifying effects due to precise, controlled and deeper tissue impact, making it a highly suitable instrument for conditions like *Vatakantaka*.

Probable Mode of Action of *Loha Shalaka*

In *Vatakantaka*, where aggravated *Vata* causes intense pain, stiffness and restricted mobility, *Loha Shalaka* serves as an effective *Agnikarma* instrument due to its strong heat-conducting nature. *Loha*, by its *Ushna* and *Tikshna* attributes, delivers sharp and penetrating heat, enabling deeper tissue stimulation. This localized thermal action liquefies morbid *Doshas*, reduces *Srotorodha* and stimulates microcirculation, thereby relieving pain and stiffness. The heat induces neurovascular responses that promote vasodilation, reduce inflammation and support functional restoration of the affected region. However, based on observations from the present study, the heat conduction from *Loha Shalaka* tends to be more intense but comparatively less sustained than *Kamsya Shalaka*. Group B participants experienced pain relief and improvement, but the relief was slightly slower and less sustained than Group A. The sharper heat impact may cause quicker superficial tissue stimulation but may not retain the heat long enough for deeper *Dhatu* involvement. This could explain the relatively milder and slower improvements seen in parameters like morning first-step pain and tenderness. Nonetheless, *Loha Shalaka* remains effective in *Agnikarma*, offering therapeutic benefits through deep penetration, *Vata*-pacification and stimulation of local circulation. The results indicate that while effective, its action may be comparatively less sustained than *Kamsya Shalaka*.

Interpretation Based on Study Findings

- Group A (*Kamsya Shalaka*) demonstrated faster and more sustained improvement in symptoms, suggesting better heat-retention, uniform diffusion and deeper action on *Mamsa* and *Snayu*.
- Group B (*Loha Shalaka*) showed improvement, but relief was relatively moderate and

required more time, possibly due to sharper but less sustained heat action

Thus, the findings of the present study indicate that while both *Shalakas* are effective, *Kamsya Shalaka* offers comparatively superior outcomes due to better thermal dynamics and deeper therapeutic effect.

CONCLUSION

The present clinical study establishes that *Agnikarma* is highly effective in treating *Vatakantaka*. Among the two instruments studied, *Kamsya Shalaka* provided superior therapeutic benefits compared to *Loha Shalaka*. While both groups showed significant clinical improvement, *Kamsya Shalaka* exhibited better efficacy in pain reduction, first-step pain improvement, and tenderness relief—both immediately after treatment and during follow-up. Thus, *Agnikarma* with *Kamsya Shalaka* can be recommended as a more effective para-surgical intervention for *Vatakantaka* and may serve as a beneficial alternative to conventional therapies for Plantar Fasciitis. The findings of this research reinforce classical *Ayurvedic* principles and contribute meaningful evidence to the therapeutic application of metal-specific *Agnikarma* in *Vata Vyadhi*.

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